

Comparison of the environmental impact of HFC and natural refrigerant transport refrigeration units from a life-cycle perspective

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the temperature-controlled transport sector has experienced a significant growth, which is expected to proceed with an even higher rate over the next few years. However, with such an expansion of the sector, the carbon footprint of transport refrigeration systems must be considered and mitigated. The overall carbon footprint of a refrigeration system can be divided into direct emissions refrigerant leakage in each process, and indirect emissions, caused by the energy consumption in each process and evaluated as the CO₂ equivalent emissions.

In this study, a simplified life cycle comparative approach is used to evaluate and compare the carbon footprint of a traditional HFC (R134a) transport refrigeration unit and of a newly developed natural refrigerant (R744) one through some selected blocks along the supply chain of the refrigerating system, including refrigerant production and recycling and unit manufacturing, operation and disposal.

During on-road operations, the environmental impact of natural refrigerant cooling units vs traditional ones will be highlighted in terms of both direct (natural refrigerant vs synthetic) and indirect (higher COP) contributions. The carbon footprint results will then be used to discuss then importance of the emissions associated with on-road operation in perspective of the system overall emissions for both the cooling units, in order to compare the systems sustainability on a larger context.

Keywords: Refrigerated transport, Life-Cycle Assessment, Carbon footprint, Carbon Dioxide, HFC.

1. INTRODUCTION

The significant growth which characterized the road transport refrigeration and the last-mile delivery sector in the last few years, and which is expected to rise at an even greater rate in the next decade, highlighted the crucial importance of an accurate assessment of the temperature-controlled transport carbon footprint, to evaluate and mitigate both the direct (linked to greenhouse gases emissions) and indirect (linked to energy consumption) emissions related to transport cooling units life cycle in its entirety.

Only a few studies related to the life-cycle environmental impact of food transport refrigeration systems are available in literature. Wu et al. (2013) presented a model to assess the carbon footprint of food transport refrigeration systems employing different refrigerants (R404A, R410A and R744) during their production, transport, use, repair and recycling phases. Li (2017) developed a numerical model based on the assessment of evaluation indexes to investigate the greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions of a R452A and of a traditional R404A food transport refrigeration systems during their entire life cycle. Wu et al. (2022a) compared the carbon footprint of a conventional vapor-compression refrigeration system with an alternative PCM-based cold storage system in refrigerated truck applications, considering also the influence of the refrigerant choice (R404A, R410A and R744).

Since literature results highlighted that the vast majority of the total lifetime carbon footprint of road transport refrigeration systems lies in the use phase, accounting for approximately 96% of a refrigerated truck's total GHG emissions (Wu et al., 2022b), in this study a dynamic numerical modelling approach has been used for the accurate evaluation, on a monthly basis, of the performance and of the actual energy demand of a R134a

and a R744 transport refrigeration units employed in urban multi-drop delivery missions, thus avoiding a parametrical evaluation, based on assumed indexes, of the energy consumption of the cooling units during operation. In addition, to evaluate and compare the environmental sustainability of road transport cooling systems employing traditional HFC refrigerants (R134a) or natural refrigerants (R744), the overall environmental impact of the life cycle of the two units will be assessed, integrating the carbon footprint linked to the operation of the cooling units with the carbon footprint linked to the refrigerants production and disposal, to the refrigerants leakage in the atmosphere and to the cooling units manufacturing and dismission.

2. THE REFRIGERATION SYSTEMS

(a)

(b)

Figure 1 – R134a cooling unit: (a) operational schematic; (b) p-h diagram of the system operating points with $T_{amb} = 30^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$.

between a two-phase ejector and a high-pressure valve (HPV) is enforced: while the ejector, characterized by a fixed geometry with a throat diameter equal to 1 mm, cannot handle the whole range of operating points (corresponding to significantly different refrigerant mass flow rates), the HPV is used to handle the mass flow rate exceeding the one processed by the ejector motive nozzle. The IHX is placed in the bypass branch connected only to the HPV valve as, according to Elbel and Hrnjak (2004), the presence of an IHX in front of the ejector motive nozzle reduces the motive flow enthalpy and, consequently, the ejector pressure lift, without increasing the cooling capacity. The mass flow rate at the outlet of the ejector-HPV parallel (5) is sent to an auxiliary evaporator, which can help providing the increase in vapor quality (6) necessary to fulfil the liquid

This study focuses on the evaluation of the environmental impact of two different cooling units, one employing a synthetic refrigerant, the other employing a natural refrigerant, both designed to provide Medium-Temperature (MT) refrigeration for the preservation of fresh or perishable goods during road transport applications.

A simple R134a vapor compression unit (Figure 1a) is considered in this study, as representative of the current road transport refrigeration sector (Tassou et al., 2009; Cavalier and Tassou, 2011; Michienau et al., 2014). Figure 1b reports the pressure-specific enthalpy (p-h) diagram of the R134a refrigerant during steady-state operation with $T_{amb} = 30^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$, with reference to Figure 1a schematic.

As an alternative of the R134a cooling unit described above, a newly developed cooling unit, which has been previously presented and described in Artuso et al. (2020) and Fabris et al. (2021) and characterized by the use of a natural fluid (R744) as the refrigerant, is considered in this study. The R744 cooling unit schematic is presented in Figure 2a. The refrigerant leaves the liquid separator in the state of saturated vapor (1a), it is superheated in the internal heat exchanger (IHX) and then it enters the compressor suction line (1b). After compression to the high-pressure level (2), the refrigerant flows in the gas cooler/condenser coils and rejects After heat rejection, a parallel

separator continuity equation and thus allowing flexibility in the ejector pressure lift choice. As extensively described in Fabris et al. (2021), the auxiliary evaporator can be bypassed to optimize the system performance as a function of environmental temperature ($5 \equiv 6$). From the separator, the vapor phase is sent to the IHX (1a), while the liquid phase (7) is expanded in a mechanical throttling valve (MTV) to the evaporation pressure (8) and then evaporated in the heat exchanger coils. The refrigerant at the outlet of the evaporator (9) is then entrained by the ejector from the main evaporator pressure level to the liquid separator pressure level. Figure 2b reports the pressure-specific enthalpy (p-h) diagram of the R744 refrigerant during steady-state operation with $T_{amb} = 30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450\text{ rev min}^{-1}$.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Refrigeration systems numerical model

A dynamic numerical model of both the cooling units is developed using the commercial multi-physics software Simcenter Amesim v.17. The numerical approach of the software is based on the discretization of real components in lumped parameters elements, connected to describe the entire system. Each element is described by nonlinear time-dependent differential equations involving the state variables. Equations are then assembled in a system of differential equations, according to the elements connection.

The compressors are modelled using a fixed displacement compressor model. From the compressors operating data available in the commercial data sheets, the different volumetric efficiency η_{vol} and the overall compression efficiency η_{comp} are interpolated as functions of the pressure ratio r_p and the rotational speed ω_{comp} . The finned-coil heat exchangers are approximated to simple straight tube in tube counter-flow configurations. The counter-flow design is then discretized into N longitudinal lumped volumes (N=6 for the R134a heat exchangers, N=10 for the R744 evaporators, N=12 for the R744 gas cooler/condenser). Internal convection between the refrigerant and the internal wall, conduction through wall and fins and external convection between the fins and the outside air are considered for each of the lumped volumes in which the heat exchangers are discretized. The heat transfer coefficients are evaluated through empirical correlations, available in the literature. For the refrigerant, mass and energy balances are evaluated in each discretized element. The R744 ejector performance is modelled using the interpolating functions reported by Banasiak et al. (2015), based on the results of an experimental evaluation of the performance of a high-pressure lift multi-ejector pack designed for R744 refrigerating systems, which describe the ejector operation as a function of the boundary conditions (motive nozzle, suction nozzle and discharge port conditions).

Figure 2 – R744 cooling unit: (a) operational schematic; (b) p-h diagram of the system operating points with $T_{amb} = 30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450\text{ rev min}^{-1}$.

A vehicle insulated body with an internal volume of 11.89 m³ is considered, for both the R134a and the R744 unit numerical models. A global heat transfer coefficient equal to $K = 0.36 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ was experimentally evaluated in a previous work (Artuso et al., 2019). The refrigerated box thermal characterization is modelled using a network of lumped thermal capacities and resistances. The dynamic internal air volume transient heat balance considers the cooling power provided by the refrigeration unit, convection with the internal wall temperature and with the transported goods, infiltrations of ambient air into the insulated body during the opening of the vehicle's doors, conductive heat through the box wall and radiation exchanges insisting on the average external surface temperature.

A detailed description of the components dimensions and geometries, as well as of the dynamic numerical modelling approach, including the formulation of the used differential equations used to describe the dynamic behaviour of the refrigeration systems, can be found in Artuso et al. (2019), Artuso et al. (2020), Fabris et al. (2021) and Fabris et al. (2022).

3.2. Refrigeration systems operation

The performance of the R134a and R744 cooling units are evaluated during operation in a fixed-structure short-range multi-drop delivery mission of temperature-controlled goods in an urban environment. The mission simulates a typical daily local distribution activity, characterized by seven doors openings for product delivery in the morning and seven in the afternoon. The mission profile is defined setting the vehicle speed, the doors openings and the amount of perishable goods discharged at each delivery point, as a function of time. The complete structure of the urban delivery mission is reported in Fabris et al. (2022).

The compressors of both the cooling units are assumed to operate at fixed speed, equal to the rated speed $\omega_{comp} = 1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$. The compressors ON/OFF control is set by a thermostat with a 4°C hysteresis, to maintain the air temperature T_i inside the refrigerated cargo space between -1°C and 3°C along the whole delivery mission.

To compare the performance of the R134a and the R744 cooling units working under the same conditions on a yearly basis, a mean day for every month in the year is considered for the numerical simulations; the climate of Athens is adopted, as representative of hot European climate. The environmental temperature, relative humidity and solar radiation intensity, available in the Energy Plus online database (Energy Plus, 2022), were collected for all the days of each month of the year, averaged hourly to obtain the climatic profile of the mean day of each of the months of the year and used as an input of the numerical models.

3.3. Life cycle evaluation

The life expectancy of road transport refrigeration units is usually limited by the operational lifetime and mileage of the vehicle (Wu et al., 2022b). In this study, the cooling units' lifetime is assumed to be 10 years (Wu et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2022a). The yearly operation is assumed to be characterized by repetitions of the same short-range delivery mission, 5 days/week for 50 weeks (Li, 2017), equally distributed in the 12 months. Within the above-mentioned lifetime, the total carbon footprint of the transport refrigeration units considered in this study is evaluated taking into account both the direct emissions, caused by refrigerant leakage, and indirect emissions, caused by the energy consumption in each process and evaluated as the CO₂ equivalent emissions, of the entire life cycle of the cooling units.

The greenhouse gas effect of a gas is measured through the Global Warming Potential, usually referred to the reference time frame of 100 years (GWP₁₀₀) and to CO₂ (GWP₁₀₀ for R744 = 1 kg_{CO₂,eq}/kg_{R134a}). The GWP₁₀₀ of R134a refrigerant is assumed to be equal to 1526 kg_{CO₂,eq}/kg_{R134a} (IPCC, 2021). The refrigerant charge of the R134a cooling unit, representative of current market small trucks and vans applications, is assumed to be equal to 2.0 kg (Tassou et al., 2009). Previous studies in literature also report that, considering a fixed cooling power production with a R744 system instead of the traditional HFC system, the R744 charge would be 1.3-2.3 times the refrigerant charge of the HFC system (Karampour and Sawalha, 2018; Aprea et al., 2012; Rossi et al., 2021). In this study a R744-HFC charge ratio equal to 2.3 kg_{R744}/kg_{HFC} is conservatively assumed. An annual leakage rate of the refrigerant during operation, compared to the total refrigerant charge, equal to 10-37% (Tassou et al., 2009), 10-25% (Li, 2017), 5-25% (Wu et al., 2022b), as well as 165% of the initial charge over a 10 years lifetime (United Nations, 2017), is reported in literature. As a representative value for the above-mentioned figures, an average annual leakage rate equal to the 15% of the total refrigerant charge is

assumed in this study. Moreover, a 2% refrigerant leakage during the assembly process and a 0.1% annual refrigerant leakage during maintenance operations are considered (Wu et al., 2013).

For the evaluation of the indirect emissions during the cooling units lifetime, the carbon footprint associated to the energy consumption of the processes of refrigerants and cooling unit production and disposal/recycling are considered in this study, as well as the fuel consumption consumed to power the cooling units and to transport the units weight onboard the vehicles. Regarding the considered refrigerants production, an overall carbon footprint of the R134a production process equal to $6.6 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}_{\text{R134a}}$ is considered (McCulloch and Lindley, 2003). Conversely, R744 is mostly recovered from industrial processes through carbon capture and storage (CCS). An average carbon footprint of the CCS process, based on different technologies, is estimated equal to $0.14 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$ (Rubin et al., 2015). In addition to CCS, a CO_2 compression and purification process is necessary to obtain a purity content of at least 95% and a limited amount of H_2O and non-condensable gases content, resulting in an additional carbon footprint linked to these processes equal to $0.04 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$ (Posch and Haider, 2012). Regarding the refrigerants disposal at the cooling units end of life, it is assumed that only 70% of the R134a refrigerant charge can be recovered and regenerated by filtering and distillation (Cascini et al., 2016). The energy requirement for refrigerant recycling is assumed equal to $4.34 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}$ (Wu et al., 2022b). The non-recoverable R134a charge is assumed to be released in the atmosphere, as well as the entirety of the R744 unit charge. Components available in the market and suitable for the specific application are selected to estimate the weight of the cooling units, resulting in a total weight of 68 kg for the R134a unit and a total weight of 156 kg for the R744 unit. Electrical energy consumption factors equal to 4.22 kWh/kg and to 2.69 kWh/kg are assumed for the cooling units manufacturing and recycling processes, respectively (Wu et al., 2022b). The carbon footprint linked to these processes is evaluated considering the average GHG emission intensity of the electricity generation in Europe, equal to $0.275 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kWh}$ (EEA, 2022). The energy consumption of the cooling units during operation is evaluated according to the results of the monthly dynamic numerical simulations of urban multi-drop delivery missions, as described in the previous sections. The cooling units are assumed to be directly driven by a belt, as most of the van-sized refrigerated vehicles (Tassou et al., 2009), directly connected to the vehicle main engine operating with diesel fuel. A diesel engine efficiency of 0.4 (Tassou et al., 2009) and a belt mechanical transmission efficiency of 0.9 are assumed. Diesel fuel is characterized by a carbon emission factor equal to $0.331 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kWh}$ (IPCC, 2022). Moreover, the carbon footprint linked to the additional fuel consumption of the vehicle engine necessary to transport the cooling units weight is evaluated assuming a fuel consumption factor per unit weight and distance equal to $2.20 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ L}/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{km})$ (IPCC, 2022).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Cooling units yearly performance

Being emissions during service the largest GHG emitter in transport vehicles (Wu et al., 2013; Li, 2017; Wu et al., 2022a), the performance of the R134a unit and of the R744 unit are firstly compared over the same short-range multi-drop delivery mission in urban environment, for each month of the year, through the definition of an average mission COP (Eq. (1)) referring to the overall energy characterizing the entire mission rather than on instantaneous power.

$$COP = \frac{E_{evap,TOT}}{E_{comp} + E_{fans}} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), $E_{evap,TOT}$ corresponds to the cooling energy delivered in the entirety of the delivery mission and $E_{comp} + E_{fans}$ corresponds to the energy consumption of the cooling unit (compressor and heat exchangers fans). The average mission COP of the R134a unit and of the R744 unit for every month of the year are reported in Table 1, while the relationship between the average mission COP of the two units and the average ambient temperature of the mission day has been highlighted in Figure 3.

The R134a average mission COP decreases almost linearly as the average external temperature increases. On the contrary, the R744 unit mission COP follows the same trend during the hottest months of the year (average external temperatures above $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), with a significantly higher COP compared to the R134a unit COP, while during the coldest months (average external temperatures below $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) the R744 unit COP decreases for decreasing ambient temperature, resulting in a lower mission COP compared to the R134a unit. The main

reason behind this behaviour for the R744 unit lies in the difference between the unit cooling capacity (the cooling power provided by the evaporators in steady-state operation) and the actual cooling demand required by the system during the dynamic operation during the mission (evaluated as the ratio between the total cooling energy provided by the evaporators and the time in which the cooling unit is actually switched on). A high difference between the rated cooling capacity of the cooling unit and the actual cooling demand required during the mission leads to a low unit duty cycle, defined as the ratio between the time in which the cooling unit is switched on and the total mission time, which has a higher impact on the overall performance of the R744 unit, as the difference between cooling capacity and cooling demand is lower in the R134a unit, thus allowing operation closer to rated conditions to the R134a unit.

Table 1 – Comparison between the average mission COP of the R134a and R744 cooling units, for every month of the year.

Month	$T_{amb,avg}$ [°C]	COP_{R134a} [-]	COP_{R744} [-]
Jan	11.6	2.01	1.75
Feb	10.4	2.12	1.83
Mar	12.3	1.95	1.75
Apr	16.6	1.65	1.83
May	21.0	1.43	2.01
Jun	26.4	1.25	1.83
Jul	28.7	1.19	1.73
Aug	29.4	1.17	1.68
Sep	25.4	1.27	1.86
Oct	20.6	1.45	1.98
Nov	15.6	1.71	1.81
Dec	11.5	2.02	1.75

Figure 3 – Average delivery mission COP for the R134a and the R744 cooling units as a function of the average ambient temperature.

Nevertheless, most of the yearly cooling energy production requirement corresponds to the months characterized by the hottest ambient temperature conditions, thus reducing the impact of the coldest months on a yearly basis. To provide the overall yearly performance of the R134a and the R744 system, the overall mission COP of the two units has been evaluated considering the total cooling energy, the total energy fed to the compressor and to the heat exchangers fans during the whole year. The yearly mission COP of the considered cooling units, as well as the total yearly cooling energy and energy consumption of the units, is then reported in Table 2. The employment of the proposed R744 unit in the considered urban delivery mission, instead of the baseline R134a unit, leads to an increase of the average mission COP equal to +27.5% on a yearly basis.

Table 2 - Comparison between the annual cooling energy production, energy consumption and average mission COP of the R134a and R744 cooling units.

Period	R134a unit			R744 unit		
	$E_{evap,TOT}$ [GJ]	$(E_{comp} + E_{fans})_{TOT}$ [GJ]	COP_{year} [-]	$E_{evap,TOT}$ [GJ]	$(E_{comp} + E_{fans})_{TOT}$ [GJ]	COP_{year} [-]
Year	5.85	4.12	1.42	6.33	3.49	1.81

4.2. Life cycle carbon footprint evaluation

To provide a complete comparison between the R134a and the R744 unit not only during their operation, but considering the entirety of their life cycle, the total equivalent CO₂ emissions of the two units are evaluated, to assess the overall environmental sustainability of the considered solutions. As discussed in Section 3.3, both the direct emissions, caused by refrigerant leakage, and the indirect emissions, caused by the energy consumption linked to refrigerants production and disposal/recycling, cooling units manufacturing, operation and recycling, as well as the additional fuel consumption consumed to transport the units weight onboard the vehicles, have been considered. The total carbon footprint of the R134a unit and R744 unit life cycle is summarized in Table 3 and in Figure 4.

Table 3 – Comparison between the total lifetime carbon footprint of the R134a and the R744 cooling unit.

Type of emissions	Process	Carbon footprint [kgCO _{2,eq}]	
		R134a unit	R744 unit
Indirect emissions	Refrigerant production	33.1	2.1
	Cooling unit manufacturing	78.9	180.7
	Operation	10521.5	8921.1
	Cooling unit additional weight	1660.0	3800.8
	Refrigerant recycling	6.1	-
	Cooling unit recycling	182.9	418.8
Direct emissions	Leakages	5585.2	11.6
TOTAL		18067.7	13335.1 (-26.2%)

Figure 4 – Total lifetime carbon footprint of the R134a cooling unit and the R744 cooling unit.

As expected, most of the CO₂ equivalent emissions of the units life cycle is linked to the energy consumption during operation (58.2% for the R134a unit and 66.9% for the R744 unit). However, the emissions linked to the additional fuel consumption required to carry the cooling units weight represent a significant portion of the units carbon footprint. In fact, due to the increased schematic complexity and components weight, the overall indirect emissions of the R744 unit are greater (+6.7%) than the R134a unit ones, despite the significant COP increase of the R744 unit during operation discussed in the previous section. This result highlights that, from a life cycle sustainability perspective, the reduction of the cooling unit weight through optimized materials choice and components design can lead to significant reductions of a transport refrigeration unit carbon footprint. Nevertheless, the R744 unit is characterized by almost null direct emissions, thanks to the choice of employing a natural refrigerant. On the contrary, a significant amount (30.9%) of the total carbon footprint of the R134a unit is linked to leakage of the refrigerant in the atmosphere, due to its high GWP. On the whole, the huge impact of the direct emissions on the R134a unit lifetime carbon footprint leads to a significant improvement of the overall environmental sustainability of the R744 unit (-26.2% of the total lifetime CO₂ equivalent emissions), highlighting the crucial importance of the employment of natural refrigerants for the upcoming future of the refrigerated transport sector.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a baseline R134a cooling unit and a newly developed R744 unit, both designed to provide MT cooling in road transport refrigeration applications, have been compared both in terms of yearly performance during operation in urban multi-drop delivery missions and in terms of overall life cycle carbon footprint, to assess the operational and environmental impact of the employment of natural refrigerants compared to

traditionally used HFC refrigerants. Dynamic numerical simulations highlighted that the R744 unit presents a higher COP during the hottest months of the year, while its performance is degraded during the coldest months. However, on a yearly basis, the R744 unit mission COP is 27.5% higher than the R134a one. Moreover, the evaluation of the total carbon footprint of the two units over their life cycle highlighted that the R744 unit presents higher indirect emissions (+6.7%) due to its weight, highlighting the importance of weight optimization. Nevertheless, the high GWP of R134a leads to significant direct emissions due to leakages, resulting in a 26.2% reduction of the total lifetime CO₂ equivalent emissions of the R744 unit. In addition, natural refrigerant CO₂ overcomes any potential or unknown negative effect on the ecosystems and human health; future work might encompass a more detailed analysis of the overall impact by means of dedicated softwares and databases.

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